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The effect of using concept maps on 8th grade students' academic achievement in the periodic table topic

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Abstract

In this study, the effect of using concept maps on the academic success of students in the 8th grade science course periodic table was investigated. The study was conducted with a total of 37 students in a secondary school in Eşme district of Uşak province. In order to determine the effectiveness of two different teaching methods (concept map technique and current curriculum), the study was based on the "pre-test post-test unequal control group design", which is a quasi-experimental research model, one of the experimental research models. The study included 1 experimental and 1 control group. There were 19 students in the experimental group and 18 students in the control group. The study took a total of 8 class hours, including the application process of the pre- and post-tests. While concept maps were used in the experimental group, they were not used in the control group. Academic achievement test was used as a data collection tool. This test was applied to both groups before and after the application. The data obtained was analyzed using the SPSS program. There was a statistical difference in the findings in favor of the experimental group.

Keywords: Science education, academic achievement, concept map, periodic table.

Introduction

Situations such as keeping up with the ever-changing age and seeking solutions to global problems increase the importance of science and technology day by day (Demirel, 2024). In this context, the science course is an important resource in terms of increasing the mentioned situations. Because natural sciences are a general expression of scientific disciplines aimed at understanding and explaining the natural world (Kuşdemir, et al., 2013). At the same time, natural sciences try to discover the laws and principles underlying these phenomena by studying phenomena in nature (Demirel & Türkmen, 2023). For this reason, the science course should include the events that take place around the students, use technology effectively and follow the developments in the scientific world (Türkhan, 2013; Demirel, 2022). In addition, in the science course, students should not only transfer knowledge, but also offer them opportunities to understand and apply scientific methods by offering them many alternative ways. This enables students to become more effective thinkers (Bozkurt, et al., 2013). Students whose thoughts develop become able to use skills such as scientific process, scientific reasoning, scientific discussion, and critical thinking during the solution of the problems encountered (Tuysuz, et al., 2013; Acat & Ay, 2014; Demirel, 2014). The more skills a student uses in science class, the more retention of knowledge increases. Thanks to permanent knowledge, students become

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academically successful, productive and more active (Tüysüz & Demirel, 2020).

Recently prepared science course curricula (MEB, 2008; MEB 2013), it is seen that these programs aim to increase students' academic success, develop their scientific process skills, positively affect their attitudes towards science, and raise technologically literate and environmentally sensitive individuals (Tuysuz, et al., 2014; Bilgin, et al., 2015). In the methods adopted in the 2018 curriculum, it is envisaged that courses will be carried out in learning environments based on the student. In this program, it was mentioned that learning environments should be designed according to research and inquiry-based learning in order for students to learn information meaningfully and permanently (MEB, 2018). According to this program, the selection of methods used is also important in order to obtain efficient results from the training process. Again, in this program, it is mentioned that the methods to be used in the courses should be careful to include connections between events and concepts. This enables students to think relationally and to reorganize their perceptions with the information they have previously acquired and record them in their memory (Ülgen, 1997; Demirel & Türkmen, 2025). One of the teaching methods that associates and structures the information in students' minds with each other and provides meaningful learning by visualizing concepts is the concept maps method.

Concept maps were first introduced to the educational literature in the early 1980s as a teaching strategy and material based on David Ausubel's theory of meaningful learning (Korkmaz, 2004). Concept maps allow information to be sent to long-term memory during meaningful learning. Sending information to long-term memory takes place in a certain order. Apart from this memory, humans also have a short-term memory. Short-term memory is weak in storing information. Concept maps contribute greatly to the retention of information by strengthening long-term memory during the schematization, encryption and visual presentation of information (All, et al., 2003). Concept maps are two-dimensional tools that show the relationships between concepts under a broader concept heading. These maps focus on individuals' learning processes and are based on meaningful learning strategies. Concept maps can be used as an effective tool for planning, teaching and evaluation at every stage of education (Kaptan 1998).

Thanks to concept maps, students become aware of their own cognitive processes while examining the relationships between concepts. At the same time, individuals can increase their level of motivation with internal control by self-evaluation (Ülgen, 1997). On the other hand, concept maps not only enable the student to learn, but also enable the teacher to teach the lesson better. Teachers can use concept maps at the end of the subject during subject teaching and to determine the level of students' achievement of goals (Kendirli, 2008). For this reason, there is no limitation on the use of concept maps in educational activities. Students at all levels from the first grade of primary school can use concept maps. In addition, concept maps can be used in different fields such as mathematics and social sciences other than science lessons (Okebukola & Jegede, 1989). Concept maps can be used especially when students organize their own knowledge, when teachers discuss the meaningfulness of concepts with students, to eliminate misunderstandings, and during the development of higher thinking skills (Novak & Gowin, 1984). However, concept maps can also be used to facilitate learning, control the learning process and reveal misconceptions (Korkmaz, 2004). The process of preparing concept maps takes place within a certain plan. Atasoy (2004) listed this planning as follows.

1. Concepts related to the subject are written in a list. No explanation is made about the concepts.
2. When creating a concept map, the most general concept is placed at the top of the page first. Then, the associated concepts are organized in a progressive manner. In the vertical editing process, concepts with similar characteristics are placed on the same line, while

other concepts are usually arranged in order of importance and placed towards the bottom of the page. This order is very critical as the concept map is prepared by taking into account the hierarchy.

3. Concepts are enclosed in round shapes so that they can be easily distinguished from other words.
4. The relationships between the concepts, generalizations and principles to be taught are listed separately.
5. In the concept map, a line is drawn between the two boxes to indicate the relationship between both concepts. To explain the relationship, a short description is written on the line.
6. The concept map is not overly inflated and complicated.

After these stages, the concept map is completed. However, some situations still need to be considered. For example, concept maps should not move from one topic to another in general. During the course, it should be ensured that previously learned information is associated with new concepts to be learned (Kaptan, 1998). It is extremely beneficial for teachers who will use concept maps in their lessons to form groups of two or three students. In this way, a strong classroom interaction is realized. In addition, concept maps are a highly valid and reliable educational tool (Novak & Gowin, 1984). Apart from these benefits, concept maps have other benefits. We can list these benefits as follows:

Concept maps are useful for students to retain information for a long time by associating them (Heinze-Fry & Novak, 1990). The primary advantage that makes the concept map method superior to others is that it can obtain a visual presentation of the main ideas (Kaptan, 1998). Concept maps help students recognize misinformation (Novak & Gowin, 1993). Concept maps improve students' perceptions of basic topics and reduce their anxiety levels about that subject (Okebula & Jedge, 1989). Concept maps enable students to understand meaningful learning (Arnaudin, et al., 1984). Concept maps also have negative aspects. If a concept map is not prepared with strong connections, when combined with a detailed test, rote learning takes place and the information disappears in a short time. However, if the connections in the concept maps are not expressed logically, the student may make mistakes between the details. In addition, the student may not understand the main structure at all because the details are not learned in detail (Atasoy, 2002). However, it is difficult to prepare concept maps. When used too often, it can become boring and lose its effectiveness. Thus, the student gets used to laziness. In addition, when concept maps are exaggerated, they move away from their purpose and may cause the loss of the learning and teaching process (Korkmaz, 2004).

In this study, the subject of the periodic table was chosen in order to show how important it is to comprehend a subject with concept maps. Among the reasons for choosing this topic are that it is thought that the concept maps method can be effective in teaching the periodic table subject, which students have difficulty in understanding, and that the elements in the periodic table can be associated with daily life. At the end of the study, an achievement test was applied to the students and it was investigated whether the concept maps were effective. The periodic table was discovered by Lothar Mayer in Germany and D. Mendeleev in Russia, unbeknownst to each other. The periodic table is a table that classifies the properties of elements into certain groups and periods, organizing the elements and facilitating the learning of their physical and chemical properties (Sienko & Plane, 1975). In this context, the research question and sub-research questions of the study are given below.

Research Question

Does the use of concept maps in the periodic table of the 8th grade science course have an effect on the academic success of the student?

Sub-Questions of the Research:

- Is there a significant difference between the pre-test academic achievement scores of the students before the application?
- Is there a significant difference between the post-test academic achievement scores of the students after the application?
- Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test academic achievement scores of the students in the experimental group?
- Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test academic achievement scores of the students in the control group?

Method

Research Design

In order to determine the effectiveness of two different teaching methods (concept map technique and current curriculum), the study is based on the "pre-test post-test unequalized control group design", which is a design of the quasi-experimental research model, which is one of the experimental research models. This pattern is used in educational research when it is difficult to assign groups unbiased (Karasar, 2010). Since the branches and numbers of the students in their schools are determined in advance, an experimental and a control group are selected from the existing classes by impartial assignment. According to this design, a pre-test is first applied to the groups; then the application is made and at the end of the application, the same tests are applied to both groups as a post-test (Tanrıöğen, 2009).

In the study, the class to which the concept maps were applied constituted the experimental group, while the class to which the current curriculum was applied constituted the control group. The application process in the experimental and control groups is shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Application Process in Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Pre-test	Process	Final test
Experimental Group	PCABT	Concept Maps	PCABT
Control Group	PCABT	Current curriculum	PCABT

Study group

The study group of the research consists of 8th grade students in a secondary school in Uşak. The study included 1 experimental and 1 control group. There were 19 students in the experimental group and 18 students in the control group.

Variables

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable of the study is the change in the academic achievement of 8th grade students after the applications.

Independent Variable

The independent variable of the study was the methods applied in the experimental and control groups.

Data Collection Tool

Periodic Table Academic Achievement Test (PCABT)

In the study, a multiple-choice test was developed by the researchers in order to determine the effect of the use of concept maps on student achievement in the 8th grade periodic table, taking into account the achievements in the current curriculum. In the final version of this test, in which validity and reliability studies are carried out, there are 25 questions consisting of four options each. The validity and reliability studies of PCABT were carried out with students who had previously learned about the periodic table. In this context, an application was carried out on 27 students studying in the 9th grade in a high school in Uşak. In order to determine the scope validity of the developed test, expert opinions were taken from 3 faculty members who are experts in the field of science education, 3 science teachers and 2 Turkish teachers to determine whether it is suitable in terms of grammar. After the necessary controls were made, the KR-20 reliability coefficient of the test was calculated as 0.79. A reliability coefficient of 0.70 and higher is generally considered sufficient in studies. The KR-20 internal consistency coefficient is one of the reliability calculation types. In this type of reliability, which is used to examine the internal consistency between the scores obtained, the calculation is made by giving 1 point for the correct answer and 0 point for the wrong answer (Büyüköztürk, 2004).

In addition to the validity and reliability of the tests to be used in the research, the distinctiveness and difficulty of the questions in the tests should also be checked. The index that shows the degree to which the questions in a test distinguish between those who know and those who do not know is called the item discrimination index and is denoted by "rj". Items with a substance distinctiveness index of 0.40 and above are included in the test. All items below 0.30 are excluded from the test. Items between 0.30 and 0.40 can also be included in the test (Ebel, 1965). In Table 2, the item discrimination index values (rjx) of the 33 questions in the PCABT are given.

Table 2.

Item distinctiveness index (rjx) values of the questions in the PCABT

Article	(rjx)	Article	(rjx)	Article	(rjx)	Article	(rjx)
1	0,78	10	0,64	19	0,57	28	0,57
2	0,35	11	0,50	20	0,57	29	0,35
3	0,64	12	0,78	21	0,35	30	0,71
4	0,28	13	0,28	22	0,21	31	0,14
5	0,42	14	0,50	23	0,78	32	0,57
6	0,21	15	0,57	24	0,21	33	0,21
7	0,64	16	0,57	25	0,28		
8	0,64	17	0,57	26	0,64		
9	0,57	18	0,71	27	0,85		

Looking at Table 2, it is seen that the distinctiveness indices of questions 4, 6, 13, 22, 24, 25, 31 and 33 are below 0.30. For this reason, the mentioned substances were excluded from the test. The total distinctiveness index of the remaining 25 questions was calculated as $R_j(\text{avg})=0.55$. Since this value is above 0.40, it can be said that the total distinctiveness of the test is good (Ebel, 1965).

In the study, the item difficulty index values of the questions in the PCABT were examined. The item difficulty index is the percentage of people who answered a question correctly. It is denoted by P. If the p value is between 0.80 and 1.00, it is a very easy question. If this value is between 0.60 and 0.79, it is easy; Between 0.40 and 0.59, it is moderate; Between 0.20 and 0.39 it is a difficult question, and between 0.0 and 0.19 it is a very difficult question (Tekin, 2000). Table 3 shows the item difficulty index (P_{jx}) values of the questions in the PCABT.

Table 3.

Item difficulty index (P_{jx}) values of the questions in the PCABT

Article	(p _{jx})	Article	(p _{jx})	Article	(p _{jx})	Article	(p _{jx})
1	0,14	10	0,42	19	0,57	28	0,57
2	0,14	11	0,42	20	0,57	29	0,71
3	0,42	12	0,42	21	0,78	30	0,57
4	0,00	13	0,42	22	0,14	31	0,28
5	0,57	14	0,42	23	0,42	32	0,57
6	0,42	15	0,85	24	0,14	33	0,42
7	0,71	16	0,57	25	0,57		
8	0,71	17	0,57	26	0,71		
9	0,57	18	0,57	27	0,28		

Looking at Table 3, after the 4th, 6th, 13th, 22nd, 24th, 25th, 31st and 33rd questions (8 in total) are removed from the test, it is seen that 1 of the remaining 25 questions is very easy, 5 of them are easy, 16 of them are moderate, 1 of them are difficult and 2 of them are very difficult. When the item difficulty index was calculated for the remaining 25 questions after 8 questions were removed from the test, P_j(avg)=0.55 was found. Since this value is between 0.40 and 0.59, we can say that PCABT has a moderate level of difficulty.

Looking at the data obtained from validity, reliability and item analysis, it is seen that PCABT is a test with high validity, reliability, good distinctiveness and medium difficulty. The analyzed PCABT was applied as a pre-test to determine whether there was a significant difference between the students' achievements in the periodic table before starting the application. Then, this test was applied as a post-test to determine whether there was a significant difference between the students' achievements depending on the method applied after the study was carried out.

Experimental Process

In this study, which was carried out in the 2012-2013 academic year, which group would be the experimental group and which group would be the control group was carried out by random assignment. In the class assigned as the experimental group, the lessons were taught using concept maps in order to improve the students' skills in the periodic table. In the control group, the same subject was covered according to the textbook approved by the Ministry of National Education (MEB). The applications in the experimental and control groups started and ended in the same week. In order to control the effect of teacher differences on students, the same teacher attended the classes in both groups.

Data Analysis

The tests used during data analysis are divided into two as parametric and non-parametric tests. The number of individuals participating in the study is important to determine which of these tests the study is suitable for. According to Yılmaz and Yılmaz (2005), it is more appropriate to use non-parametric tests instead of parametric tests in the comparison of samples with less than 30 people. Since there were 19 students in the experimental group of this study, non-parametric tests were used during the analysis. Of these tests, Mann Whitney U was used for unrelated groups, while Wilcoxon signed ranks test was used for related groups.

Ethics Committee Permission

In accordance with the circular dated 07.03.2012 and numbered B.08.0.YET.00.20.00.0/3616 of the General Directorate of Innovation and Educational Technologies, the study on research permission in institutions affiliated to the MEM numbered 29425508/605.01 and dated 15.02.2013 was evaluated and it was deemed appropriate to be implemented at the time intervals deemed appropriate by the school administration.

Findings

Findings of the First Sub-Problem

In this section, the findings of the sub-research problem "Is there a significant difference between the pre-test academic achievement scores of the students before the application?" are included. During the solution of the problem, Mann Whitney U from the non-parametric statistical method was used. Table 4 shows the analysis results of the Mann Whitney U test.

Table 4.

Mann Whitney U test findings on comparison of preliminary PCABT scores of experimental and control groups

Groups	N	Rank average	Sum of Rows	U	Z	p
Experimental Group	19	18,71	355,50	165,500	-0,168	0,866
Control Group	18	19,31	347,50			

* $p > 0.05$

From the findings in Table 4, it is seen that there is no statistically significant difference between the preliminary PCABT scores of the students in the experimental and control groups ($Z = -0.168$; $p = 0.866$; $p > 0.05$). In addition, the mean rank of the preliminary PCABT scores of the students in the experimental group was 18.71; The mean rank of the preliminary PCABT scores of the students in the control group was found to be 19.31. This finding shows that the rank averages of the preliminary PCABT scores of the experimental and control group students have similar values. This shows that the preliminary PCABT success levels of the experimental and control groups were equal.

Findings of the Second Sub-Problem

In this section, the findings of the sub-research problem "Is there a significant difference between the post-test academic achievement scores of the students after the application?" are included. During the solution of the problem, Mann Whitney U from the non-parametric statistical method was used. Table 5 shows the Mann Whitney U test analysis results.

Table 5.

Mann Whitney U test findings on comparison of the final PCABT scores of experimental and control group students

Groups	N	Rank average	Sum of Rows	U	Z	p
Experimental Group	19	22,87	434,50	97,500	-2,240	0,025
Control Group	18	14,92	268,50			

*p<0.05

From the data in Table 5, it is seen that there is a statistically significant difference between the final PCABT scores of the students in the experimental and control groups in favor of the experimental group ($Z=-2.240$; $p=0.025$; $p<0.05$). This finding shows that there is a significant difference between the final PCABT scores of the experimental and control groups, where there is no statistically significant difference between the preliminary PCABT scores. In addition, the mean rank of the last PCABT scores of the students in the experimental group was 22.87; The mean rank of the last PCABT scores of the students in the control group was found to be 14.92. This result shows that the academic achievement averages of the students in the experimental group were higher than the students in the control group.

Findings of the Third Sub-Problem

In this section, "Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test academic achievement scores of the students in the experimental group?" findings of the sub-research problem are included. During the solution of this problem, Wilcoxon signed rank test, one of the non-parametric statistical tests, was used. The findings obtained from this test are given in Table 6.

Table 6.

Wilcoxon test results for the comparison of pre- and post-PCABT scores of experimental group students

Academic Achievement Posttest - Pretest	N	Rank Average	Sum of Rows	Z	p
Negative Rank	17	9,00	153,00		
Positive Rank	0	0,00	0,00	-3,629	0,000*
Even	2				

*p<0.001

When the findings in Table 6 are examined, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the pre- and post-PCABT scores of the experimental group students ($Z=-3.629$; $p=0.000$; $p<0.001$). In addition, the sum of the negative ranks of the students in the experimental group was 153.00; The sum of the positive ranks was found to be 0.00. According to the rank totals of the difference scores, there was a difference in favor of negative ranks. In other words, the post-test scores of the experimental group are higher than the control group. According to these findings, it is seen that the use of concept maps in the course makes a significant contribution to the academic success of the students in the experimental group.

Findings of the Fourth Sub-Problem

In this section, "Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test academic achievement scores of the students in the control group?" findings of the sub-research problem are included. During the solution of this problem, Wilcoxon signed rank test, one of the non-parametric statistical tests, was used. The findings obtained from this test are given in Table 7.

Table 7.

Wilcoxon test results for comparison of pre- and post-PCABT scores of control group students

Academic Achievement Posttest - Pretest	N	Rank Average	Sum of Rows	Z	p
Negative Rank	17	9,00	121,00	-3,629	0,000*
Positive Rank	0	0,00	32,00		
Even	2				

$p < 0.05$

When the findings in Table 7 are examined, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the pre- and post-PCABT scores of the students in the control group ($Z = -2.114$; $p = 0.034$; $p < 0.05$). The total PCABT negative ranks of the students in the control group were 121.00; the sum of the positive ranks was found to be 32.00. As a result of the analysis, when the rank totals of the difference scores are taken into account, it is seen that this observed difference is in favor of negative ranks, in other words, the post-test scores of the control group. From this finding, it is seen that the concept maps created to develop the skills related to the periodic table subject were not used, and the students in the control group, where the teaching was carried out as stipulated by the curriculum, also achieved a significant increase in their academic achievement levels.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

In this section, the results obtained from the findings regarding the question "Does the use of concept maps in the periodic table of the 8th grade science and technology course have an effect on the academic achievement of the students?" are discussed within the framework of the relevant literature. In order to find the answer to this research question, the Mann-Whitney U and Wilcoxon signed-rank test, which are non-parametric statistical tests, were applied to the data obtained from the experimental and control groups.

When the findings of the first sub-study problem of the study were examined, no significant difference was found between the preliminary PCABT scores of the students in the experimental and control groups. This shows that the pre-test academic achievement levels of the experimental and control groups are approximately equal. This result obtained from the study is based on the studies examining the effects of teaching science subjects with concept maps on the achievement of students at different grade levels (Çömek, et al., 2016; Kara & Kefeli, 2018; Gökçen-Özgün & Yalçın, 2019; Öztürk, 2019). In this context, Çömek, et al. (2016) investigated the effect of the use of concept maps on students' academic achievement in the "Light and Sound" unit of the 6th grade science course in their study. From the findings, it was determined that there was no significant difference between the pre-test scores of the students. Kara & Kefeli (2018) determined that there was no statistical difference between students' preliminary academic achievements in the 7th grade science course taught using concept maps. Gökçen-

Özgün & Yalçın (2019) investigated the effect of using concept maps in general biology course on the academic achievement of pre-service teachers. From the findings, it was determined that there was no significant difference between the preliminary academic achievements of the students.

When the findings of the second sub-research problem of the study were examined, it was concluded that there was a significant difference between the final PCABT scores of the students in the experimental and control groups in favor of the experimental group to which the concept maps were applied. Studies supporting this result (Öztürk, 2019; Mert, 2019; Kaymaz, 2022) are found in the relevant literature. In his study, Öztürk (2019) investigated the effect of concept maps on student achievement in teaching the subject of substance transport in plants. From the findings he obtained, he determined that the student success in the course taught with a concept map and by drawing a concept map to the groups significantly differed from the student success in the course taught with the traditional method. Mert (2019) investigated the effect of the concept map method on the academic achievement of high school students in teaching. From the findings he obtained, he found a statistical difference in the group where the lessons were taught according to the concept map compared to the group taught according to the current curriculum. Kaymaz (2022), on the other hand, covered the subject of cells and divisions with the concept maps technique in the 7th grade science course. From the findings obtained, it was determined that the academic achievement of the students in the courses taught with the concept map technique was statistically more significant than the student success in the courses taught according to the science curriculum.

When the findings of the third sub-research problem of the study are examined, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the academic achievement pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group students ($Z = -3.629$; $p = 0.000$; $p < 0.001$). The sum of the negative ranks of the academic achievement test of the students in the experimental group was found to be 153.00 and the sum of the positive ranks was 0.00. When the rank totals of the difference scores are examined, it is seen that the difference is in favor of the negative ranks, that is, in favor of the post-test scores of the experimental group. According to the findings, the use of concept maps in the lessons significantly increased the academic success of the students. In the literature, studies supporting the findings regarding this sub-problem of the research (Kul, 2019; Öztürk, 2019; Kaymaz, 2022; Duru, 2023; Efil, 2023). In his study, Kul (2019) investigated the effect of concept maps on sixth grade students' learning of the unit "Our Earth, the Moon and Our Source of Life, the Sun". From the findings he obtained, he determined that concept maps made positive contributions to students' academic achievement, permanence of knowledge and concept development. Kaymaz (2022) compared the pre-test averages and post-test averages of the students in the experimental group using the concept map. From the findings, it was determined that teaching with the support of concept maps increased student success statistically significantly. In his study, Duru (2023) investigated the effect of using concept maps on student achievement in the field of active citizenship learning in 7th grade social studies lessons. From the findings obtained in this study, in which the pre- and post-test scores were compared, it was determined that the student scores in the course taught with the concept map method differed significantly. In his study, Efil (2023) investigated the effect of concept maps used in the cooperative learning model on students' success in acids-bases. From the findings obtained, it was determined that the academic achievements of the students in the course carried out with the support of the concept map differed significantly according to the course taught according to the current curriculum.

When the findings of the fourth sub-research problem of the study are examined, it is seen that there is a significant difference between the academic achievement pre- and post-test scores of the students in the control group ($Z = -2.114$; $p = 0.034$; $p < 0.05$). The sum of the negative ranks

of the students in the control group was found to be 121.00 and the sum of the positive ranks was 32.00. As a result of the analysis, when the rank totals of the difference scores are taken into account, it is seen that this observed difference is in favor of negative ranks, in other words, the post-test scores of the control group. According to the findings, it was observed that the students in the control group, where the concept maps created to develop the skills related to the periodic table were not used, and the teaching was carried out as stipulated by the curriculum, provided a significant increase in the academic achievement levels. In the literature, studies supporting the findings regarding this sub-question of the research (Öztürk, 2019; Printer 2020; Kaymaz, 2022). In his study, Öztürk (2019) found a statistically significant difference between the pre- and post-test academic achievement scores of the students in the 12th grade biology course, where the concept map was not used and the traditional curriculum was applied. In his study, Yazıcı (2020) investigated the effect of using concept maps on academic success in teaching English to 1st year university students. Concept maps were not used in the courses in the control group, where the traditional teaching method was used. From the findings obtained, it was determined that the traditional teaching method created a significant difference on the students. In his study, Kaymaz (2022) covered the subject of cells and divisions in the science course in the control group, where the lessons were taught according to the current program. From the findings of the academic achievement pre-test results and post-test results, he determined a statistically significant increase in the post-test success averages of the students.

Concepts are the building blocks of information and concepts must be learned in order for learning to take place. Students create science concepts in their minds in their outdoor lives. If the acquired concept is wrong or incomplete, subsequent learning becomes difficult. Therefore, the method used should both eliminate mislearning and help to find relationships between concepts. One of these methods is the concept map creation technique. Concept maps make it easier for students to learn the concepts they have trouble with, as well as eliminate misconceptions.

Based on the findings obtained in this context, various recommendations can be made for educators, program developers, textbook authors and education policy makers:

- Science and technology teachers can be trained on the creation of concept maps and their use as course materials.
- Concept maps can be included more in guidebooks prepared for teachers in science and technology lessons.
- At the end of the subject and unit, more space can be given to general concept maps covering all critical concepts in it.
- Without expanding concept maps too much, it can be ensured that previously acquired knowledge is associated with new concepts.
- Care should be taken to use concept maps in accordance with the level of the students and the targeted result.
- The use of concept maps should not be limited to a specific lesson stage, but should be applied in various parts of the course.
- Carrying out the learning-teaching process by using the concept map technique rather than traditional methods can make the lessons more enjoyable.
- Students should be informed about how concept maps are used before starting the lessons.
- A concept map can often be used to identify students' misconceptions and deficiencies about a subject.

- In this study, in which concept maps were investigated, a measurement tool was used for the academic achievement of the students. In addition to this measurement tool, other tools can be used in the studies to be carried out.

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